

A methodology for obtaining a pointing model in the early stages of telecom dish into radiotelescope conversion projects.

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Abstract. By the beginning of the 21st Century, a considerable number of large (~ 15 - 30 m) antennas built for satellite telecommunications had become obsolete and were taken out of service around the globe. This situation led groups and institutions in various countries to convert these antennas into radiotelescopes, both for single-dish operation and as part of very long baseline interferometry (VLBI) networks. Such an example is Uruguay, a country with no previous experience in professional radio astronomy. In this article we present a methodology for obtaining a pointing model for an antenna to be converted into a radiotelescope, in the early stages of the project. The methodology is advantageous when the available receiver is not sensitive enough to detect radio sources other than the Sun (and possibly the Moon), which is often the case in the early stages of conversion projects. For this purpose, we developed a simple radiometer based on commercial off-the-shelf components, which we used to obtain a pointing model for a 4.2-m antenna located at Manga Earth Station (MES, latitude -34.8039° N, longitude -56.1406° E). We achieved an RMS accuracy equal to the antenna control unit's resolution (0.1°). This work can easily be extrapolated to larger antennas, and so constitutes the first step in the conversion of larger dishes available at MES (16.4-m and 32-m) into radio telescopes.

Keywords: radio astronomy, pointing model, radiometer, drift-scan.

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1 Introduction

Teleports for international telecommunications built around the globe during the late 1960's and 70's were comprised of antennas that, due to the receiver technology available at the time, required large (~ 30 -m) primary reflectors. In the following decades, more sensitive receivers enabled the use of medium-sized (~ 15 -m) antennas to achieve the same performance as the previous large-sized infrastructure. The development of fiber optics for communication links in the 1990's began a process of decreasing communications traffic through satellite earth stations, which up to that point concentrated all of the different countries' international communications at a single point. These industry trends eventually led to the obsolescence of a large portion of the infrastructure at the teleports, and in many cases even to the complete closure of these facilities.¹

As a consequence, an increasing number of antennas became available for other uses — e.g., radio astronomy. Among the first telecommunication antennas (TA) converted to radio telescopes (RT) were the 30-m dish of the Ceduna Earth Station in Australia,² in 1995 and another 30-m dish near Atlanta in the United States.¹ These initiatives were followed by the conversions at Yamaguchi, in Japan,³ Sicaya, in Perú,⁴ Goonhilly, in the UK,⁵ Warkworth, in New Zealand⁶ and Kuntunse, in Ghana.⁷ All of these projects involve 30-m to 32-m antennas. More recently, South Africa has played a leading role in a number of conversion projects in Africa, most notably Ghana where the conversion has been completed. In other countries in Southern (Tanzania, Zambia and Angola) and Eastern (Madagascar, Mozambique and Kenya) Africa, feasibility studies and first steps have been taken in the conversion of TA to RT, as shown by presentations at the *Dish Conversion Workshop*ⁱ, held in Ghana in 2019. Furthermore, most of these countries (Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Madagascar, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia, Zambia and South Africa) have joined to form the *African VLBI Network (AVN)*.⁷

A similar initiative was formed as an outgrowth of the DRAGN workshops, namely the Ibero-American VLBI Initiative (IVIA), which initially involved groups and institutions from eight Latin American countries (Mexico, Costa Rica, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, Brazil, Argentina and Uruguay), plus Spain and Portugal. At present, Mexico has almost completed its conversion project at Tulancingo (state of Hidalgo), which involves a 32-m antenna equipped with a warm L-band (1400-1800 MHz) and a cooled (cryogenic) C-band (4-8 GHz) receiver.⁸ The Costa Rican team, with support from the Instituto Nacional de Astrofísica, Óptica y Electrónica in Mexico, has nearly completed the conversion of an 11-m antenna, which will be used for solar physics.

ⁱOne of four workshops held during 2019 as part of the UK's Global Challenges Research Fund project *Development through Radio Astronomy Global Network*, led by the University of Leeds with the participation of the Universities of Hertfordshire, Manchester, Oxford, Bristol and Central Lancashire (www.dragn.info).

In 2019 the Uruguayan team analyzed the feasibility of converting the 32-m dish at Manga Earth Station (MES), and proposed a conversion project that included a room-temperature receiver covering the methanol line at 6.7 GHz, a modern drive system, and corrective maintenance on the backup structure, primary reflector, and sub-reflector. This project was not funded, but instead an agreement was reached in 2023 between the University of the Republic of Uruguay and the state-owned telecom company ANTEL (which owns MES) through which the research team obtained access and support from the local technical staff to use a 16.4-m and a 4.2-m antenna. Due to a mechanical malfunction, the larger 16.4 m dish is currently frozen in elevation (at 43.6°) but moves freely within its northerly azimuth range of 34° west of the north through 45° east of the north. The smaller 4.2-m antenna has a broader range of movement, with an elevation range of 17.5° to 65° and an azimuth range of -90° to $+90^\circ$ with respect to North. This flexibility in positioning motivated its use in the present work.

For initial tests of the 4.2-m antenna, we developed a simple radiometer based on a diode detector to use in conjunction with the original telecommunications LNB. Using this radiometer, we made preliminary observations to obtain a pointing model (PM) for the antenna.

This article presents the main results of these activities and is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the hardware setup used, in particular the antenna system and the locally designed radiometer. Section 3 describes the basic principles of pointing models and the methodology we used to acquire the data to develop the model. Section 4 presents the results and discussion for the PM as well as drift scans generated with the PM applied. Conclusions and future activities are outlined in Section 5.

2 Hardware setup

The principle hardware of our setup was a 4.2-m prime focus antenna designed and used for satellite communications, and a locally built radiometer based on an off-the-shelf diode power detector. Both of these subsystems are described in the following subsections.

2.1 4.2-m antenna

The 4.2-m prime focus antenna is shown in Figure 1. It is currently one of two identical backup antennas for a 6.3-m Vertex antenna providing connectivity to Uruguay’s Antarctic Scientific Base.

Fig 1: 4.2-m prime focus antenna, with C- and Ku-band receivers, manufactured by *DH Satellite*.

The antenna’s azimuth coverage is -50.0° to $+60.2^\circ$ E, and its elevation coverage is 17.5° to 65° . The main technical specifications of the antenna are listed in Table 1. From the manufacturer’s value for the half-power beam width (HPBW) reported at 4 GHz, we find the relation of the aperture D to the HPBW of the primary beam to be

Parameter	Value
Antenna sections	8
f/d ratio	0.34
First sidelobe (C-band)	2.1°
HPBW (C-band)	1.2°
C-band gain	43.5 dB
Ku-band gain	53.0 dB

Table 1: Main technical specifications of the 4.2-m antenna.

Parameter	C band	Ku band
RF band	3.40 – 4.20 GHz	10.95 – 12.15 GHz
LO frequency	5.15 GHz	10.00 GHz
IF band	950 – 1750 MHz	950 – 2150 MHz
Gain	62 dB typ., 55 dB min., 70 dB max.	60 dB typ., 52 dB min., 65 dB max.
Gain fluctuation	≤6dB p-p max.	≤5dB p-p typ.
Noise temp. (at ambient temp.)	20K typ., 24K Max.	50.7K

Table 2: Main technical specifications of the LNBS at C- and Ku-band.

$$\theta_{HPBW} = 1.17 \cdot \frac{\lambda}{D} \quad (1)$$

This value for the numerical coefficient corresponds to a 10 dB edge taper. Assuming the same coefficient for Ku-band we obtain a HPBW of 0.4° at 11.55 GHz, which is consistent with the reported Ku-band gain. The aperture efficiency of a 10dB taper is 82%, so the effective area is 11.3 m².

The antenna is equipped with both C- and Ku-band receivers, whose frontends and feeds are shown in Figure 2. The technical specifications for the C- and Ku-band LNBS are shown in Table 2.

2.2 Radiometer design

This section describes the hardware and software of a locally designed simple radiometer that covers a nominal passband of 1.8 – 6.0 GHz. A primary design goal was to develop low-cost

Fig 2: Antenna feeds located at the primary focus of the main reflector. **mencionamos fabricantes o modelos de los LNBS aqui.**

equipment for antenna characterization in the early stages of TA to RT conversion projects.

The heart of the radiometer is the MiniCircuits ZX47-60LN+ power detector, that converts total RF power between 10-8000 MHz into an output voltage between 0.5-2.10V, with a nominal slope of -25 mV/dB. The voltage response versus input power curves for different frequencies is shown in Figure 3.

The detector output is connected to an analog input of an Arduino UNO development board. The detector also has an internal temperature sensor, whose signal is connected to another of the Arduino's analog inputs.

The Arduino board is in turn connected to a mini PC via USB cable, which also powers the board. All components are housed in an IP65 waterproof PVC box, measuring $170 \times 170 \times 75$ mm (see Figure 4).

The code loaded into the microcontroller calculates and outputs the average of ten readings from the analog inputs, with each reading spaced 10 ms apart. The effective period of data output

Fig 3: Response curves of the MiniCircuits ZX47-60LN+ power detector (Figure source: manufacturer’s data sheet).

on the serial port is therefore 100 ms. After each read-out, "flushing" of data on the serial port is carried out, via the *Arduino serial.flush* function, to avoid overflow issues of the data buffer.

The mini PC connected to the Arduino board runs Windows 7, and two Python scripts are executed on it. The first (*main1.py*) reads from the serial port at a period set by the user at startup, and assigns each sample the UNIX time (expressed in seconds elapsed since 1970-01-01 00:00:00 UTC) obtained from the PC clock. This clock is synchronized by the *NetTime* applicationⁱⁱ. The second script (*main2.py*) displays the data in real time, with a time window set by the user. All these scripts are available via a *git-hub* repository.ⁱⁱⁱ

The radiometer was installed in the control room of the 4.2-m antenna at MES, connected to

ⁱⁱ Available at <https://www.timesynctool.com/>

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://github.com/jmcaldas/radiometer>.

the Ku-band LNB IF output signal. After a series of tests, it was deemed convenient to include an additional amplification stage at the radiometer input, using a MiniCircuits LNA model ZX60-63GLN+. The main technical characteristics of this amplifier are shown in Table 3, and an image of the interior of the radiometer is shown in Figure 4. Although the power detector covers a passband of 10 to 8000 MHz, the ZX60-63GLN+ amplifier has a nominal passband of 1800 to 6000 MHz, thus setting the overall bandwidth response of the radiometer.

A 16-bit HiLetgo ADS1115 ADC was purchased to provide a higher resolution than that offered by the Arduino UNO’s built-in ADC (10 bit). It was not included in the prototype but rather has been left as a future improvement.

Parameter	Value
Noise figure	0.9 dB
Gain	28-31.5 dB
Input return loss	6 dB
Output IP3	27.8 dBm
Output return loss	10 dB
Operating voltage	5.0 V

Table 3: Main features of the MiniCircuits ZX60-63GLN+ LNA. All values correspond to 1.8 GHz as specified in the manufacturer’s datasheet.

3 Pointing model

3.1 Model description

A pointing model comprises a function $f(A,E)$ that converts desired coordinates (A,E) into coordinates commanded to the antenna control unit (A_{ACU}, E_{ACU}) . A pointing model seeks to minimize the pointing errors $\epsilon_A = abs(A - A_{ap})$ and $\epsilon_E = abs(E - E_{ap})$, where the subscripts "ap" refer to the actual pointing of the antenna.

Pointing errors in radio astronomy contribute significantly to the sensitivity of the system as a whole: an error of half the antenna HPBW attenuates the desired signal by 3 dB, which in this

Fig 4: Inside view of the radiometer.

context can mean non-detection of the desired signal. On the other hand, a pointing error of 10% of the HPBW attenuates the signal by only 0.12 dB (97% of the maximum), which is usually acceptable and in fact is commonly adopted as the upper limit of the tolerable RMS error for any pointing model (see e.g., ⁹¹⁰).

We use the pointing model described in ¹¹. In this model, the horizontal (δh) and vertical (δv) corrections, defined respectively as $\delta h = \delta A \cos(E)$ and $\delta v = \delta E$, where $\delta A = A_{ACU} - A$ and $\delta E = E_{ACU} - E$, are given by equations 2 and 3.

$$\delta h = P_1 \cos(E) + P_2 + P_3 \sin(E) + P_4 \cos(A) \sin(E) + P_5 \sin(A) \sin(E) + P_6 \sin(A) \quad (2)$$

Parameter	Description
P_1	AZ encoder offset.
P_2	Collimation error.
P_3	Inclination of EL axis.
P_4	N-S Inclination of AZ axis.
P_5	E-W Inclination of AZ axis.
P_6	Coordinate errors.
P_7	EL encoder offset.
P_8	Gravity deformation.
P_9	Gravity deformation.

Table 4: Physical meaning of the PM model, as described in.¹¹

$$\delta v = -P_4 \sin(A) + P_5 \cos(A) + P_6 \cos(A) \sin(E) + P_7 + P_8 \cos(E) + P_9 \sin(E) \quad (3)$$

The model considers the transformation between an astronomical Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) , where z indicates the direction of the local zenith, and an instrumental system (x', y', z') .

A detailed mathematical description can be found in.¹²

All the model parameters P_i have a physical meaning. The offsets of the azimuth and elevation encoders are expressed by the parameters P_1 and P_7 , respectively. The collimation error (P_2) accounts for the non-orthogonality of the reflector optical axis and the elevation axis, as well as misalignment between the optical axis and the azimuth axis in stow position ($E=90^\circ$). The non-orthogonality between the azimuth and elevation axes is reflected in the parameter P_3 , while P_4 and P_5 specify the inclination (tilt) of the azimuth axis. The parameters P_8 and P_9 are linked to the gravitational deformation of the antenna structure, which is a function of elevation, and which causes the optical axis to deviate from the direction of the elevation axis. Finally, the parameter P_6 reflects the errors in the coordinates considered "true". The parameters and their physical meaning are summarized in Table 4.

The usual way of generating pairs of points (A_i, E_i) and their corresponding $(A_{ACU,i}, E_{ACU,i})$ necessary to fit the pointing model, is by making cross-scans in azimuth and elevation of a strong point source, recording the signal output at five positions around the maximum and fitting a three-dimensional parabola to these five points. The vertex of this parabola defines the Az/El corrections to be applied at the nominal position of the given source. This procedure is described in detail in¹² (see their Appendix). Revisions of this methodology, as e.g.,¹¹ show that the parameter P_6 associated with uncertainties in "true" source positions, may be neglected altogether now that very precise positions are available, for example, through VLBI observations.

With fully-commissioned radio telescopes, such pointing scans are generally an automated procedure, and can be done even with relatively weak sources (with flux densities of order a few Janskys). In the early stages of a conversion project, however, the existing ACU may not be accessible for programming. Moreover, the original telecommunications receivers will lack the sensitivity to detect astronomical sources other than the Sun and the Moon. Both of these conditions apply to our conversion project, thus we devised an alternative method based on manual adjustments to nominal pointing positions of the Sun until the maximum radiometer response is obtained. When this value is reached, the time and the corresponding ACU coordinates are recorded. The recorded times are translated into horizontal coordinates for the Sun using the implementation of the algorithm described in¹³ and contained in the MATLAB *AstroPack* package¹⁴ (available at ^{iv}), which is a numerical approximation to analytical equations. The reported accuracy is 1.08".

Although the solar position as a function of time is known to quite high precision, our method of manually pointing for maximum radiometer response may introduce a non-negligible error that can be accounted for by the P_6 parameter.

^{iv}<https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/128984-astropack-maattv2>

Finally, the least squares solution to the over-determined system of linear equations generated from Equations 2 and 3 is found, through MATLAB's built-in function *linsolve*, which uses QR-factorization. The solution is the set of model parameters P_i .

3.2 Synthetic model

In order to analyze the dataset needed to generate a PM of acceptable accuracy over the antenna's movement range, we first generated a synthetic model, i.e., a model with known (and arbitrary) parameters P_i . Then, we computed the solar positions (A_i, E_i) every 10 minutes between 10:00 and 14:00 local time, once a week, starting on August 21st, 2024. Next, we converted these points to $(A_{ACU,i}, E_{ACU,i})$ using the known model. Finally, we added random noise to each computed $(A_{ACU,i}, E_{ACU,i})$ ($\mu = 0, \sigma = 0.1^\circ$) to obtain simulated $(A'_{ACU,i}, E'_{ACU,i})$. We then fitted a model to (A_i, E_i) and these clone data points $(A'_{ACU,i}, E'_{ACU,i})$. This yielded a PM of parameters P'_i , which was applied to points uniformly spaced over the entire moving range of the antenna. These coordinates were then compared to those calculated with the original PM of parameters P_i . The comparison was made by computing the error ϵ_i given by

$$\epsilon_i = \sqrt{[\cos(E_{ACU,i})(A_{ACU,i} - A'_{ACU,i})]^2 + (E_{ACU,i} - E'_{ACU,i})^2} \quad (4)$$

This procedure was carried out for four distinct datasets, comprising 4, 6, 8 and 10 days, spanning 4, 6, 8 and 10 weeks, respectively. For each dataset, the simulation was run 100 times and the average errors ϵ_i were recorded for each computed sky position.

The results are shown in Figures 5a-5d, which show the average errors (in $^\circ$) for each dataset across the entire moving range of the antenna. These figures also show the solar positions being

used in each case, and contour lines correspond to 1/10 of the antenna’s HPBW in Ku- (black) and C-band (red).

As these figures show, the 10-week dataset is able to generate a PM with an accuracy greater than 1/10 of the C-band HPBW (0.12°) practically across the entire moving range. With 6 weeks of data we obtain an accuracy better than 1/10 of the C-band HPBW across the entire azimuth range, above an elevation of $\sim 30^\circ$.

An acceptable region of accuracy better than 1/10 of the Ku-band HPBW is achieved inside a region enclosing the datapoints used to build the model, as the figures show. Now, since the antenna will initially operate mainly in C-band (at least until an LNB with a passband covering the 12.2 GHz methanol line is purchased), we limited our procedure to a 6-week collection period; these results are presented in the next section.

These simulations are suggestive and encouraging but they are by no means ”conclusive”. Rather, they are indicative of what pointing error can be expected but do not rule out the possibility of greater errors and the need of manual fine tuning.

4 Results and discussion

Using the proposed methodology for six days (spaced over 6 weeks) we report here the resulting PM. Also, we validate these results by applying the PM to solar and lunar positions and making drift scans of these sources.

4.1 Pointing model

Figures 6a and 6b show the corrections in azimuth and elevation ($\Delta A = A_{PM} - A$, $\Delta E = E_{PM} - E$), respectively, throughout the antenna’s moving range of $[-90.0^\circ; +90^\circ]$ in azimuth,

(a) 4 week-data.

(b) 6 week-data.

(c) 8 week-data.

(d) 10 week-data.

Fig 5: Filled contour maps of errors ϵ_i in $^\circ$ (see text for further details) obtained over the antenna's moving range, for each dataset of the simulations. Yellow dots indicate solar positions used in the simulations, and contour lines indicate 1/10 of the Ku- (black) and C-band (red) HPBW.

[17.5 $^\circ$; 65 $^\circ$] in elevation. The units of the corrections are degrees. Figures 7a and 7b show azimuth and elevation returned by the model, based on the corresponding data Az_{ACU} , E_{ACU} .

The resulting parameters $P_1 - P_9$ are shown in Table 5. The quality of the PM is quantified by assigning the following error to each data point i (which corresponds to a unique Az/El pointing position on the sky)

$$\epsilon_i = \sqrt{[\cos(E)(A_{i,d} - A_{i,m})]^2 + (E_{i,d} - E_{i,m})^2} \quad (5)$$

(a) $\Delta A = A_{PM} - A$

(b) $\Delta E = E_{PM} - E$

Fig 6: Azimuth (a) and elevation (b) corrections applied by the model throughout the antenna’s moving range. Yellow dots indicate datapoints (i.e., solar positions) used to fit the model.

Fig 7: ”Model vs. real” plots, in azimuth (a) and elevation (b). Red solid lines are $y=x$ curves.

where the subscripts ’d’ and ’m’ refer to the data used to build the model and the data returned by the model, respectively. The RMS error, ϵ_i , as well as the mean absolute errors (MAE) in each coordinate are indicated in Table 6. Both tables contain the results corresponding to the entire available sample of points (143), and to a subsample generated from an iterative elimination of outliers, where in each iteration the point with the greatest error is eliminated, until a fixed RMS (in this case the ACU resolution, 0.1°) or a minimum number of data points is reached. As the tables show, an RMS equal to the ACU’s resolution is achieved with 134 data points (268 equations).

Parameter	Entire sample	Subsample
# points	143	134
P_1	-2.20	-0.04
P_2	4.11	0.70
P_3	-3.37	-0.71
P_4	-0.22	-0.22
P_5	0.53	0.62
P_6	-0.32	-0.41
P_7	12.44	12.33
P_8	-8.60	-8.60
P_9	-9.45	-9.40

Table 5: Parameter values (in degrees) of the PM. The third column corresponds to the subsample obtained after the iterative outlier elimination process (see text).

Parameter	Entire sample	Subsample
# points	143	134
RMS [°]	0.16	0.10
MAE, AZ [°]	0.14	0.09
MAE, EL [°]	0.05	0.05

Table 6: Performance metrics for the obtained PM. The third column corresponds to the subsample obtained after the iterative outlier elimination process (see text).

MAE below 1/10 of the HPBW in C band is achieved both in azimuth and elevation, even for the full sample.

Geostationary (GEO) satellites may be used to slightly widen the sky coverage of the data points used to build the PM, when the system is not sensitive enough to detect other radio sources. The ephemerides of GEO satellites are well-known and available online (e.g., n2yo.com, dishpointer.com).

4.2 Validation

To test and validate the obtained PM, we carried out drift scans of the Sun in C band, by pointing the antenna first at a nominal position as given by the solar ephemeris. Shortly after the drift scan, the antenna was re-pointed at the Sun’s new position, with the Az/El correction as given by the PM. This was done on two dates, November 6 and December 6 (see Table 7).

Date and time of drift scan UT	Az _{JPL} [°]	El _{JPL} [°]	Az _{PM} [°]	El _{PM} [°]	Az _{ACU} [°]	El _{ACU} [°]
2024-Nov-06 13:30	62.4265	57.7070	62.6	57.8	†62.4	57.7
2024-Nov-06 13:50	56.0128	61.2388	56.2	61.5	‡56.2	61.5
2024-Dec-06 13:25	75.5972	59.0006	75.9	59.1	†75.6	59.0
2024-Dec-06 13:40	71.9390	61.9570	72.3	62.3	‡72.3	62.3

Table 7: Solar ephemeris generated by *JPL Horizons* (<https://ssd.jpl.nasa.gov/horizons/app.html#/>) (columns 1-3), corresponding pointing positions generated by the PM (columns 4-5) and positions commanded to the ACU (columns 6-7). † PM not applied; ACU values are truncated JPL values. ‡ PM applied; ACU values are given by the PM.

The solar ephemeris was obtained with the *Horizons* web tool of the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL)^v. The closest angular separation between the pointing directions on November 6 and the data points used for the PM was $\sim 10^\circ$, while on December 6 it was $\sim 17^\circ$.

The results of the drift scans are shown in Figure 8 for November 6 (8a) and December 6 (8b). On each date, the first drift scan corresponds to an uncorrected position (i.e., the pointing position as given by the ephemeris), while the second drift scan corresponds to the corrected position as given by the PM.

The difference in peak power between the uncorrected and corrected drift scans was ~ 0.6 dB and ~ 1.0 dB for November 6 and December 6, respectively. These values are of the expected magnitude: as seen in Table 7, the pointing corrections are about one-third of the HPBW. For a Gaussian beam, this implies ~ 1 dB of power loss.

To test the PM further, we performed drift scans of the Moon in Ku-band at sky positions where the angular corrections given by the PM were considerable — in this case close to one HPBW (0.4°). These are shown in Table 8. The closest angular distance from the first position to the model data points was $\sim 5^\circ$, and $\sim 10^\circ$ for the second one.

For the first drift scan (December 11), we applied the corrections given by the "full model",

^vAvailable (10/4/2024) [here](#)

Fig 8: Solar drift scans on (a) 11/06 and (b) 12/06 in C-band, obtained first with no PM correction and shortly after applying the PM.

Date and time of drift scan UT	AZ_{JPL} [$^{\circ}$]	El_{JPL} [$^{\circ}$]	AZ_{PM} [$^{\circ}$]	El_{PM} [$^{\circ}$]	AZ_{ACU} [$^{\circ}$]	El_{ACU} [$^{\circ}$]	PM Model
2024-Dec-11 22:01:00	40.0730	28.9585	40.566	29.696	40.6	29.7	Full
2024-Dec-13 01:22:30	0.0900	33.0034	0.277	33.406	0.3	33.4	Subsample

Table 8: Moon’s ephemeris generated by *JPL Horizons* (columns 1-3), corresponding pointing positions generated by the PM (columns 4-5) and positions commanded to the ACU (columns 6-7).

while for the second drift scan we applied the corrections given by the ”subsample model” described in 3.

The results are shown in Figures 9a and 9b for the December 11 and December 12 drift scans, respectively. As can be seen, there is no significant difference in signal level between the two; in both cases the peak is ~ 2 dB above the noise floor.

The azimuth correction given by the ”full model” for the second drift scan was 0.5° , while the ”subsample model” gave 0.3° , that is, a difference of $1/2$ HPBW. If we had applied the ”full model” we would have had an attenuation of about 3 dB and not detected the source.

Fig 9: Moon drift scans on 12/11 and 12/12 in Ku-band, obtained after applying the "full model" PM (a) and the "subsample model" (b).

5 Conclusions

We present a methodology to obtain a pointing model for a 4.2m antenna available for radio astronomy at Manga Earth Station in Uruguay, using a simple radiometer and the original telecommunications frontend and ACU. We achieved an RMS pointing error for the antenna of 0.16° , which is slightly more than 1/10 of the antenna's HPBW at C band (0.12°), and the ACU's resolution (0.1°), using the full available dataset of 143 data points. This methodology can be implemented on the larger antennas available at MES and may prove useful to other groups in the early stages of an antenna conversion project.

The simple radiometer, along with the pointing model methodology, allow us to use the 4.2m antenna as a functional radio telescope for undergraduate training in radio astronomy. In turn, the experience acquired through these activities will allow us to address the characterization of the 16.4m antenna, and its subsequent use as a scientific instrument.

It is our hope that the results presented here will serve as an example of initial tasks that can be undertaken in early stages of a conversion project, especially when little or no financial support is

available and inexpensive commercial off-the-shelf components are used.

Disclosures

The authors have no relevant financial interests in the manuscript and no potential conflicts of interest to disclose.

Code, Data, and Materials Availability

All Python scripts as well as Arduino code developed for the radiometer are available at the author's *github* repository: <https://github.com/jmcaldas/radiometer>

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